

DEVELOPMENT OF LIBRARY CULTURE OF FUTURE PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract. *In this article, in addition to determining the effective ways of developing the reading culture of future primary school teachers of higher pedagogical educational institutions and choosing its specific content, it is necessary to study books in the educational process of future specialists. Effective concrete methods and means of increasing the love of children, developing the culture of reading are shown. The article also provides information on the importance of reading in our republic today.*

Keywords: *book, reader, culture, spirituality, psyche, perfect, politics, attention, expert, education, upbringing, psychological, scientist, vocabulary, speech, thinking, ability, development.*

Introduction. One of the most important factors in raising a child is book reading. The core of the words "book", "reading", "library" is actually derived from Arabic and serves one purpose, that is, to enrich human spirituality. The reforms implemented in our country to increase the reading culture of young people are not in vain, therefore, the maturity of the future generation is determined by learning and being educated.

In this regard, on January 12, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, announced an order "Aimed at increasing book reading and reading culture". This, in turn, is an important factor contributing to the increase in the level of reading in our country and the publication of new books with content. Using such opportunities wisely, reading rich works that are newly published, allows young people to develop their consciousness, deepen their thinking, and have their own independent opinion. It should also be noted that the 5 initiatives put forward by our president have become an important factor that further supports the youth today. The important program "Organization of systematic work on raising the spirituality of young people and widely promoting reading among them" is being implemented.

Acquaintance with a book, reading it gives a person a special pleasure. While reading, the reader gets to know the book more closely, begins to form an idea about its scientific and artistic value, thinks, and improves the culture of reading.

Due to the special attention paid by the president to the promotion of reading culture, in general schools, universities, all educational institutions, "Young Reader", "Kirobkhanlar Bayrami", viewing contests, and recreation centers are opened. Stores and libraries opening in remote villages are important in meeting the spiritual and intellectual needs of the young generation and in getting familiar with books.

The essence of the book is eternal... This essence makes thinking eternal.

Research object and used methods

The process of using technologies that serve to develop reading culture among students of higher education institutions was defined as the object of the research. The methods of observation, analysis and summarization of materials, group and individual interviews, surveys (oral) were used to cover the research topic.

The obtained results and their analysis.

As the great poet and thinker Alisher Navoi wrote, "a book is a grateful teacher, the most important source of knowledge and spiritual growth". There are many proverbs in the language of our people about the importance of reading books, getting proper education, and learning a profession. For example, "A mind without a book is a bird without wings", "Knowledge is a lamp of the mind", "Beauty is knowledge in enlightenment". Such wise sayings can be continued for a long time. For thousands of years, it has been showing people the right path, and an important factor in their being educated, professional, and certainly happy is to be friends with books, and to enjoy reading books. Books have a special place in the lives of young people. Because a good book increases a person's feelings of love for the homeland, respect for national and universal values, and encourages goodness.

In recent years in our country, the scope of work on the promotion of reading culture among young people has increased to a qualitative level. In particular, the decision of the President of Uzbekistan dated September 13, 2017 "On the program of comprehensive measures to develop the system of publication and distribution of book products, increase and promote book reading and reading culture", the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 781 of December 14, 2020, the national program for the development and support of reading culture in 2020-2025 and a number of other documents serve as a program for the development of the industry.

Developing a system for evaluating the effectiveness of the measures implemented in the development of reading, introducing ratings such as "The best reading area", "The best reading neighborhood", "The best reading educational institution" and other important tasks have been defined.

The culture of reading ensures that a person can fully understand the source, enjoy it, understand and evaluate the author's thoughts and ideas. Reading a book directs a person to directly engage in practice, harmonize with life, and receive spiritual benefits. The word "mutolaa" means reading in Arabic, and today it means a wider concept than reading a book.

Books convey the masterpieces of human thought to many generations. Indeed, no other source can enhance human maturity like books. Each reader will have the opportunity to read artistic works or scientific works based on his age group, and to understand the ideas that have been discussed more deeply. For this, the child's interests should be thoroughly studied in cooperation with parents, kindergarten, and school. As they say, parents have seven neighborhoods for one child, everyone is equally responsible for their upbringing and their spiritual and cultural development. It is not for nothing that they say that a family that is not in the habit of reading books is a spiritually poor family. Therefore, not only parents, but also library staff should be experts in their profession and choose the right books for readers, taking into account their interests.

In the pedagogy of children's reading, the growth of reading according to age is divided into the following stages: childhood 6-9 years; transition from childhood to adolescence 10-11 years; adolescence 12-13 years old; the transition from adolescence to adolescence is considered to be 14 years. The age limit of people in this category is flexible, that is, according to the formation of the socio-psychological conditions of the book reader, a 10-year-old child can be added to the category of a teenage reader depending on the unique typological characteristics, and a 14-year-old reader is a reader transitioning to adolescence. It will be possible to add to the list of the nature of the category. In order for reading to enter the spiritual life of a child, it is necessary to have an

effective and aesthetic preparation in advance. The task of the librarian is to know the reader and the book well.

If we look at the history of our dear friend, the book has come a long way to its current form. A few thousand years ago, ancient Babylonians, Assyrians and other peoples of the ancient world used ceramics as books. In China, the first books were written on bamboo plates. Later, they invented writing on silk in China, and writing on paper in the 1st century AD.

In Egypt, one of the cradles of ancient culture, the first book texts were engraved on stone pieces. The book "Avesta", one of the examples of the high culture of the people of the East, was originally written on parchment made from 12,000 cattle skins. In the Middle Ages, parchment or papyrus sheets were folded into four and made into a notebook (tetrad, Greek "four"). The books created by combining several such notebooks are called "Codex". The codices were the first step in the book's current form. At the end of the 1st century AD, the first mentions of parchment codes appear - in fact, books consisting of pages.

Despite their superiority over writing, they became widespread only by the 3rd century AD. Every year, 755,755 new books are published in the world. Since the middle of 2017, 134,399,411 books have been published worldwide. These numbers are not just numbers, they are the result of efforts made to make our young people mature.

"The book takes you to a world you haven't seen yet, tells you words you haven't heard," says Getsen. In fact, the book is rich in many mysteries. His riches are incomparable. The book gives wings to a person. When talking about the culture of reading books, first of all, it is necessary to give information and understanding to young people about the rules and types of reading books.

Reading is a complex type of speech activity, which has two aspects: that is, the technical aspect - acquiring the skills of reading and fast reading, and the creative aspect - obtaining the necessary information from the text.

After all, a book is a lamp of the soul, a wing of thought. In particular, it is a pleasure to read a book and think about its content with peers, feeling the unique pleasant smell that is emanating from a printed book and cannot be found in an electronic edition, and being filled with endless pleasure from the mysterious rustling of miraculous pages while turning the page.

In the words of the author Amir Temur, "The book (bitig) is the basis of all creativity and intelligence, knowledge, a teacher who creates life". In this sense, regardless of the form, all books serve to promote our national identity and universal human values. A book is the nourishment of our psyche, making friends with it not only elevates a person, but also introduces him to the world, accompanies him, and leads him to goodness. A person who reads a book sharpens his mind, enriches his spirituality and leads to maturity.

Today, the tradition of reading books is a bit behind. Our modern youth are busy with phone or computer games rather than reading books. In a modern country it is good to keep up with the times, but one cannot get the nourishment one gets from a book in anything else.

In fact, conditions are being created for popularizing the reading culture among young people, increasing their artistic literacy and creating a reading environment. The fact that the fourth initiative of the 5 important initiatives put forward by the President is aimed at organizing systematic work on raising the morale of young people and widely promoting reading among them is a clear proof of the attention to book reading.

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Today, in many households, almost no time is devoted to family reading. In most families, the owner of the house is always busy with work, so after dinner, they either sit down by the window to write about the tiredness of the day, or they prefer to sleep to relax. There are even families where parents themselves prefer to spend time at home with their phone or computer rather than with their child. Instead of putting up with their children's whims, being emotionally close to them, and taking an interest in their achievements and problems, their studies are entrusted to their teachers or only their mastery of academic subjects is monitored, education and upbringing will be mainly the work of teachers and trainers in educational institutions. For the rest of the day, the child who is left alone or unsupervised mainly prepares an independent lesson. He spends most of his time, but spends his days not realizing the essence of the shows he has watched and the knowledge he has studied. The saddest thing is that nowadays most of the young people have a strong place in the memory of various types of mobile communication devices or computer equipment. If a child does not know how to read something, if he does not listen to what he reads or does not understand the essence, then he cannot get any knowledge and pleasure from it, so he cannot get any aesthetic pleasure and spiritual energy from such illicit games, on the contrary, thoughtfulness. A number of other negative vices such as irritability, nervousness, indifference, irresponsibility, laziness, lack of purpose are formed and become more and more strong in the psyche and character.

A great scholar, a true patriot, a teacher with high potential, Najmuddin Kubro, said, "I saw success in effort, and failure in indifference and laziness". Therefore, the heads of the family should pay attention to the fate of the children, they should start reading age-appropriate books with the children and hold family conversations about the works read, the knowledge gained, their place and importance in human life, they should pay more attention to listening to the feedback of their sons and daughters, support them, and correct their shortcomings gently. This situation not only helps in the development of book-loving children in the family, but also in the formation of a friendly atmosphere among family members, strengthening respect for parents and self-confidence, reasoning, responsibility, accountability, it also serves as a unique foundation for cultivating the qualities of frugality, valuing time.

Therefore, every parent should pay special attention to their child's not only physical, but also mental and spiritual upbringing, provide them with art books suitable for their age, exchange ideas with them about the books they have read. "We need to give our young people a decent education and realize their aspirations for science. For this purpose, we need to develop the system of pre-school education, to fundamentally improve the material and technical base of secondary and family educational institutions, and the quality of scientific and educational processes," says our head of state. Education cannot be imagined without books. In the process of education, both the student and the teacher feel the need to read books directly. It's gratifying, of course. But nowadays, students mainly use scientific literature, textbooks and manuals, so they have limited opportunities to devote time to reading works of art. The student is grasping works of art only to fulfill the task given by the teacher in the literature class. As a result, it is known: the process of reading becomes not a hobby, but an obligation. A student who has not developed a passion for reading books since childhood does not find the strength, does not feel enthusiasm, does not

express a desire to read the large-scale works given to him later, he only gets to know the abbreviated excerpt given in the textbook and the pathos, ideological and artistic purpose of the writer, which he instilled in the entire content of the work. There are many negative consequences of low education: the ability of independent thinking, deep perception of reality, the ability to react to events, and the ability to distinguish between black and white are not fully formed; will not be familiar with national culture, history and traditions; spiritual poverty and weakness arise; when faced with problems in life, it is difficult to find a solution, he considers himself without will; his literacy is low, he cannot fully express his thoughts due to his lack of vocabulary; he faces difficulties in creating a compositionally perfect text that meets the requirements for cultural speech (such as clarity, correctness, logical consistency, coherence, purity, etc.), and in composing sentences. As a proof of this, we can say that when we write essays, statements, and dictations in the native language and literature classes, we see many spellings, punctuation, and stylistic errors in the written work of most students, and the level of creative work of most students is very low. When we talk to students, they cannot say when was the last time they read a work of art, and when we are interested in the list of works of art they have read, unfortunately, their names are few and far between. In order to eliminate such problems, we assign the students to read a work of art with a certain name every week, and we study the ideological and artistic aspects of that work with the students of the group within the specified period.

When we analyze the works given for independent reading, we can witness that the student's desire to read fiction books increases, and that surprise and pleasure appear in him. Therefore, in order to satisfy the spiritual needs of the young generation, it is necessary to regularly teach them how to choose a book, read it, analyze it, and for this, in our opinion, it is necessary to increase the number of hours of classes in the subjects of literature and mother tongue, to divide the classes into groups. As a result of this, the possibility of individual approach to students will increase, and the effectiveness of classes will be increased. Also, students have more conversations with expert teachers and learn from them. Literary classes are full of anthropology, psychology, and ethics qualities in the process of education and training of truly patriotic, potential, courageous young people, ideologically and intellectually mature personnel, meeting the necessary spiritual needs.

Summary

Undoubtedly, the needs of people are increasing, but in any era, the value of spiritual needs increases and never disappears. Spiritual decline causes the decline of society, and spiritual perfection serves as the main solid foundation for the development of society.

In conclusion, it can be said that the book is one of the closest friends. We find answers to questions through books, books are the most important food for thought. Books offer the best intellectual recreation and flight of imagination. In the words of Ernest Hemingway: A good book is like an iceberg, seven or eight of them live under water.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Buyuk kelajagimizni mard va olijanob xalqimiz bilan birga quramiz. – T.: O‘zbekiston, 2017. – 488 b.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “O‘zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo‘yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to‘g‘risida”gi Farmoni. // Harakatlar strategiyasi asosida

- jadal taraqqiyot va yangilanish sari. – T.: G‘afur G‘ulom nomidagi nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi, 2017. – 92 b.
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi. – “Zarafshon”, 2018-yil 29-dekabr, 155-156-son.
 4. G‘oziev E. O‘quvchilarning o‘quv faoliyatini boshqarish. – Toshkent: O‘qituvchi, 1988. – 104 b.
 5. Alisher Navoiyning “Mahbub ul qulub” asari.
 6. Ochilov M. Yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar. - Qarshi. “Nasaf”, 2000 y.-80 b.
 7. Vishnyakova N.F. Kreativnaya psixopedagogika. Psixologiya tvorcheskogo obucheniya. – Minsk: Izd. NIORB «Poli Big», 1995. –S. 129.